

The meaning of climate-smart forestry— A narrative literature review

Elaine Anne Parlade^{*} , Gerhard Weiss

Institute of Forest, Environmental, and Natural Resource Policy, Department of Economics and Social Sciences, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU), Feistmantelstrasse 4, 1180 Vienna, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Climate change
Sustainable forest management
Forest governance
Climate governance
Systematic literature review

ABSTRACT

Climate-Smart Forestry (CSF) has gained prominence as a concept for addressing climate change in forestry, yet its meaning and application vary across the scientific literature. This paper examines how CSF is conceptualized through a PRISMA-guided systematic review combined with thematic narrative analysis of 32 scientific publications published between 2015 and 2025. The analysis identifies four recurring narrative clusters that structure how climate-related problems, actors, solutions, and future forest visions are articulated. Across these clusters, CSF emerges as a flexible, integrative concept anchored in mitigation and adaptation objectives but differentiated in terms of its treatment of forest management, governance, and the social dimension. Findings also reveal that policy and governance actors are consistently foregrounded, although local knowledge and differentiated actor roles receive limited attention. While social dimensions are more frequently referenced within CSF scholarship, distributional and power-related questions concerning how benefits, risks, responsibilities, and decision-making authority are allocated are rarely examined in depth. As the concept expands to incorporate biodiversity and broader sustainability objectives, a clearer articulation of trade-offs among mitigation, adaptation, production, and socio-economic goals becomes increasingly important. Making these recurring narrative configurations explicit helps clarify how CSF maintains coherence while accommodating divergent interpretations, with implications for more reflexive climate-oriented forest governance.

1. Introduction

Forests have long provided societies with a wide range of ecosystem services that support human well-being, livelihoods, biodiversity, and climate regulation (MEA, 2005). In global climate debates, their role in carbon storage and sequestration has made them central to land-based mitigation strategies (EC, 2019; Nijnik, 2010). At the same time, climate change is increasingly disrupting forest ecosystems by altering disturbance regimes and increasing uncertainty surrounding forest development and management outcomes (Seidl et al., 2014, 2017). Intensifying wildfires, storms, and pest outbreaks challenge longstanding assumptions of forest stability and predictability, and threaten the continued provision of ecosystem services and societal benefits (IPCC, 2014; Lindner et al., 2010; Senf and Seidl, 2021).

This creates a central tension for forest-based climate action. Achieving international climate goals requires rapid reductions in greenhouse gas emissions as well as the strengthening of natural carbon sinks, placing attention on land-use systems, including forests, within broader decarbonization pathways (Rockström et al., 2017). However,

the contribution of forests to mitigation can itself be compromised by climate-related disturbances that threaten carbon persistence and long-term forest resilience (Lindner et al., 2010; Seidl et al., 2014, 2017). Forest governance thus faces the challenge of addressing mitigation and adaptation together, while also considering the social and economic conditions through which forest management decisions are made and implemented.

International policy agendas have increasingly positioned forests as a key component of integrated climate mitigation, adaptation, and resilience strategies (United Nations, 2015a; UNFCCC, 2021; EC, 2021). In Europe, this policy emphasis is closely connected to the role of forests as carbon sinks and contributors to regional climate mitigation objectives (EC, 2019). It also reflects a broader “climatization” of forest governance, whereby forests are often understood primarily in relation to climate mitigation and carbon dynamics (Singer and Giessen, 2017; Pülzl et al., 2024). Alongside this, global sustainability frameworks emphasize that climate objectives must be pursued through sustainable forest management, rather than through carbon-focused strategies alone (United Nations, 2015b).

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: aineparlade@boku.ac.at (E.A. Parlade), gerhard.weiss@boku.ac.at (G. Weiss).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2026.103854>

Received 7 April 2026; Received in revised form 15 June 2026; Accepted 24 June 2026

Available online 30 June 2026

1389-9341/© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

In light of these evolving challenges and frameworks, a range of concepts and approaches has been proposed to guide forest management in a climate change context, including sustainable forest management, close-to-nature forestry, forest and landscape restoration, ecosystem-based adaptation, climate-resilient forestry, and Climate-Smart Forestry (CSF). These concepts partly overlap in their attention to resilience, multifunctionality, restoration, carbon storage, biodiversity, and social benefits, while differing in their emphasis, policy origins, and preferred management responses. Within this broader conceptual landscape, CSF has become increasingly prominent in both scientific and policy discussions as an approach to addressing climate objectives in forestry (Nabuurs et al., 2017; Bowditch et al., 2020; Verkerk et al., 2020).

In this paper, CSF is understood as an integrative forest governance and management concept that seeks to align mitigation, adaptation, and social dimensions of forestry within broader sustainability objectives. Its interpretation and application throughout the literature, however, reflect diverse perspectives on forests' roles in climate change, the relative importance of different objectives, and the actors responsible for implementing them. Within this evolving landscape, recent reviews point to conceptual ambiguity and divergent operational interpretations of CSF, including differences in how CSF is positioned in relation to sustainable forest management and how its goals are translated into indicators, practices, and envisioned futures (Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023; Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022).

Such differences can be understood as narrative and discursive variations that structure how challenges are interpreted, which actors are prioritized, and what forms of action are considered legitimate (Winkel, 2012; Wittmayer et al., 2019). Narratives assemble events, actors, and causal relations into coherent storylines through which complex phenomena become intelligible (Hajer, 1995; Roe, 1994). By selecting what is emphasized and how developments are linked over time, they implicitly privilege certain knowledge claims and normative commitments while marginalizing others, thereby orienting attention towards particular futures and pathways of change (Stone, 1989; Fischer and Forester, 1993, as cited in Leibold et al., 2024). Examining CSF narratives, therefore, makes it possible to assess how the concept is constructed in the scientific literature and what governance assumptions underpin its use.

Despite the analytical value of examining narratives and the increasing visibility of CSF, the narrative structures underpinning its scientific discussion have not yet been thoroughly analyzed. Much of the existing literature remains focused on the technical, biophysical, or implementation-oriented aspects of CSF, with underlying assumptions and value orientations comparatively underexplored (Alawode et al., 2026). To address this gap, this paper undertakes a systematic literature review combined with thematic narrative analysis. The study is guided by three research questions: (RQ1) How is CSF conceptualized in the scientific literature? (RQ2) What patterns of convergence and divergence characterize these conceptualizations? (RQ3) What governance implications arise from these patterns? These questions are operationalized through a narrative framework that examines problem interpretations, actors and agency, proposed solutions, envisioned forest futures, and CSF pillar emphasis.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 outlines the conceptual foundations of CSF, while Section 3 introduces the analytical framework guiding the review. Section 4 then describes the methodological approach, including the literature search, screening, and analytical procedures. Section 5 presents the reviewed literature and the identified narrative clusters. Section 6 examines patterns of convergence and divergence across these narratives and discusses their implications for climate-oriented forest governance. The paper concludes by reflecting on how narrative analysis helps clarify the governance dimensions of the CSF concept.

2. Conceptual origins of climate-smart forestry

CSF draws conceptually from Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA), which emerged from growing concern about the dual relationship between agriculture and climate change and was formalized by the FAO and the World Bank in 2010 following the 2007–2008 food crisis (FAO, 2013; Chandra et al., 2018). CSA is commonly articulated through three linked objectives: sustainably increasing productivity, strengthening adaptation, and reducing or removing greenhouse gas emissions (FAO, 2013; Lipper et al., 2014). This integrated three-pillar logic later informed debates in the forest sector, including the development of the CSF concept.

CSF also has roots in longer-standing forest science debates concerning the role of forests in the global carbon cycle and their contribution to climate mitigation (Weatherall et al., 2022). Long before CSF emerged, forestry research had already recognized the role of forests in the global carbon cycle and their relevance to climate mitigation. Early atmospheric evidence linked seasonal CO₂ dynamics to terrestrial biosphere processes (Keeling, 1960 as cited in Weatherall et al., 2022), and subsequent work quantified the importance of forests as major carbon pools with significant mitigation potential (Dixon et al., 1994 as cited in Weatherall et al., 2022). Building on these foundations, CSF emerged as a concept that explicitly links climate mitigation and adaptation objectives to forest management decisions.

Early formulations of CSF were therefore strongly mitigation-oriented. Influential mid-2010s contributions articulated CSF primarily in terms of enhancing forest carbon sinks and optimizing wood use for climate benefits (Nabuurs et al., 2015; Kauppi et al., 2018). However, as climate-related disturbances such as droughts, pests, and storms intensified, attention increasingly shifted towards forest resilience and adaptive capacity (Lindner et al., 2010). This shift broadened the concept by positioning adaptation not only as a separate objective, but also as a prerequisite for sustaining mitigation potential and forest functions over time (Nabuurs et al., 2017; Verkerk et al., 2020). This broadening also shaped how CSF became positioned in relation to Sustainable Forest Management (SFM). Most contributions now present CSF not as a replacement for SFM, but as a climate-oriented refinement that foregrounds mitigation and adaptation within established multifunctional management principles. In this sense, CSF can be understood as building on SFM while placing greater emphasis on climate change, carbon dynamics, adaptive capacity, and long-term forest resilience.

Over time, the concept has broadened further to include social and governance dimensions. Building on a collaborative definition-building process, Bowditch et al. (2020) identify adaptation, mitigation, and social dimensions as the core focus of CSF and stress the need to integrate these dimensions rather than develop them in isolation. This understanding is subsequently consolidated by Weatherall et al. (2022), who present the CLIMO definition of CSF through three main pillars comprising adaptation to climate change, mitigation of climate change,

Fig. 1. Three Pillars of Climate-Smart Forestry (adapted from Weatherall et al., 2022, based on the definition developed in Bowditch et al., 2020).

and the social dimension (see Fig. 1). Several recent studies reflect this broader understanding of CSF, although the relative emphasis placed on each pillar continues to vary across the literature (e.g., Santopuoli et al., 2021; Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022; Alfieri et al., 2024). From a mitigation-centered framing, CSF has therefore evolved towards a more integrative concept with a shared climate-oriented foundation but multiple interpretations of its aims, emphases, and relationship to SFM (Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023). This combination of coherence and variation provides the basis for the analytical approach adopted in this paper, which examines how the three core pillars are articulated alongside broader narrative elements across the CSF literature.

3. Analytical lens: Narrative perspective on CSF

The conceptual variation surrounding CSF calls for an analytical lens that can examine not only how the concept is defined, but also how it is made meaningful across different scientific contributions. This review therefore adopts a narrative perspective to examine how CSF is articulated across the scientific literature. Instead of treating CSF as a fixed concept or unified framework, the analysis focuses on recurring narrative configurations (Wittmayer et al., 2019; Leipold et al., 2024) through which mitigation, adaptation, and social dimensions are connected, prioritized, and justified.

The review draws on Wittmayer et al.'s (2019) tripartite analytical framework for *Narratives of Change (NoC)*, which distinguishes between narrative content, narrative construction, and the role of narratives. This review primarily focuses on the content dimension comprising: (i) rationale, including problem description and desired future, (ii) actors, and (iii) a plot that orders developments and interventions in a meaningful way. These content components were adapted to the CSF literature through five analytical dimensions: problem interpretation, actors and agency, proposed solutions, envisioned futures, and CSF pillar emphasis. The first four dimensions translate Wittmayer et al.'s content components into questions suited to the CSF literature, while the fifth dimension captures how the three commonly cited CSF pillars of mitigation, adaptation, and the social dimension are emphasized within these narrative configurations.

The inclusion of CSF pillar emphasis as a fifth analytical dimension is informed by Chandra et al.'s (2018) analysis of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA). Part of their study examines how CSA is structured around multiple pillars, particularly adaptation, mitigation, and food security, and how these pillars are emphasized and integrated differently across global, developing-country, and developed-country narratives. This provided a methodological inspiration for examining whether CSF publications articulate mitigation, adaptation, and social dimensions in a balanced way, prioritize some dimensions over others, or leave particular dimensions comparatively underdeveloped.

This analytical structure provides a systematic basis for addressing the study's research questions. It supports RQ1 by examining how CSF is conceptualized through climate-related problem interpretations, attributed actor responsibilities, proposed management solutions, and envisioned forest futures. Additionally, it supports RQ2 by enabling comparison of where these narrative elements converge or diverge across the literature. This comparison is consequential for governance because narratives condense complexity and orient action under conditions of uncertainty (Wittmayer et al., 2019; Hajer, 1995). In forest policy research, such interpretive structures shape how problems are understood, which objectives are foregrounded, and which governance approaches are considered legitimate (Arts et al., 2010; Winkel, 2012).

Furthermore, narratives are treated here as analytical constructs that cut across publications rather than as reflections of individual author intentions. Narrative-based synthesis in sustainability research has demonstrated the value of this approach for clarifying contested policy concepts and identifying areas of convergence and divergence within scientific fields (Leipold et al., 2023, 2024). Applied to CSF, this perspective enables a structured comparison of recurring narrative

configurations across the literature and provides the basis for identifying narrative clusters and assessing their governance implications in relation to RQ3.

4. Methods

The study combines a systematic literature review with a thematic narrative analysis to identify a set of CSF publications and examine how the CSF concept is constructed and differentiated across the scientific literature. Literature identification and screening followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021). Drawing on the narrative analytical framework outlined in Section 3, the analysis examined problem interpretations, actors and agency, proposed solutions, envisioned forest futures, and CSF pillar emphasis. These analytical dimensions were used to identify how CSF is conceptualized across publications (RQ1), assess patterns of convergence and divergence (RQ2), and consider the governance implications arising from these patterns (RQ3).

4.1. Literature search and database construction

A structured literature search was conducted on 22 May 2025 using the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection, selected for its coverage of peer-reviewed research in forestry, climate change, and environmental governance. Records were retrieved through the Topic Search field (titles, abstracts, and author keywords) using the following query: *TS = ("climate-smart forestry" OR "climate smart forestry" OR "climate-smart forest management")*.

The query was deliberately restricted to these terms to capture publications that explicitly engage with CSF as a defined concept. Broader or adjacent terms (e.g., "resilience", "climate-oriented forest management", "sustainable forest management") were excluded to avoid conflating CSF with related but distinct frameworks or management paradigms. This also means that broader uses of CSF embedded within adjacent frameworks, such as grey literature discussing forestry within the climate-smart agriculture and development agenda, were not included in the coded database. This procedure yielded 84 English-language records published between 2015 and 2025.

To reflect the global distribution of CSF scholarship within the selected timeframe, no geographical restrictions were applied. An additional 13 records were identified through citation searching, which included three foundational European Forest Institute (EFI) science-policy reports (i.e., Nabuurs et al., 2015; Nabuurs et al., 2018; Kauppi et al., 2018) that played a formative role in introducing and consolidating the CSF concept in the European forest-sector literature. Although these reports are not peer-reviewed in the conventional academic sense, they were retained due to their influence on later scientific and policy-oriented literature. No other grey literature or policy-sourcebook materials were added through citation searching. This decision kept the review focused on scientific literature while retaining a small number of formative science-policy reports that directly shaped the subsequent CSF literature. The combined dataset comprised 96 records after duplicates were removed.

4.2. Screening process

The screening followed a two-stage process consistent with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines. First, titles and abstracts were reviewed to identify publications requiring closer assessment. The initial title and abstract screening was conducted by the first author, with ambiguous cases discussed with the second author. No records were excluded at this stage, and all 96 publications were retained for full-text assessment.

Second, full texts were assessed to determine whether they explicitly conceptualized, defined, or applied CSF in ways relevant to forest policy and governance debates. Publications were excluded if CSF was mentioned only peripherally, if their focus was primarily technical or

operational without substantive engagement with the CSF concept, or if they were not substantively concerned with CSF. Full-text screening decisions were recorded in a Microsoft Excel screening table, which included reasons for exclusion where applicable. Book chapters were treated as individual publications, and the three EFI science-policy reports were retained because they directly introduced or elaborated the CSF concept. This process resulted in a final dataset of 32 publications. The number of records identified, excluded, and retained at each stage is presented in the PRISMA flow diagram (Fig. 2).

4.3. Analytical approach

The narrative analysis drew on the analytical elements outlined in Section 3 and combined theory-guided deductive coding with inductive thematic refinement. Deductive coding applied five predefined analytical categories derived from the narrative framework and the three-pillar understanding of CSF. Inductive coding was then used within each category to identify recurring themes and patterns that emerged through repeated reading and comparison across the publications. The first author conducted the coding, while the second author reviewed the coding framework, discussed selected coded examples, and contributed to refining the categories and interpreting the resulting narrative clusters. Coding was conducted manually using Microsoft Excel, which allowed coded summaries, analytical notes, and cluster assignments to be compared across publications.

Drawing on the narrative content component of Wittmayer et al. (2019), publications were coded along four adapted analytical dimensions:

- Problem interpretation: how climate change, forests, and associated challenges are interpreted
- Actors and agency: how responsibility and capacity for action are attributed
- Proposed solutions: practices, policies, or management approaches emphasized
- Envisioned future: desired trajectories or outcomes associated with CSF.

In addition, a fifth analytical category was used:

- CSF pillar emphasis: relative emphasis on mitigation, adaptation, and the social dimension, as articulated within the CSF concept.

The inclusion of the fifth category was informed by Chandra et al., (2018), who examined how the pillars of CSA are emphasized and integrated across different narratives. Each publication was coded for these five elements, with attention to how they appeared together as coherent configurations within individual texts. An example coding matrix is provided in Annex A.

In addition to narrative content coding, each publication was classified according to its primary source/mode of knowledge production (Conceptual, Modeling, Empirical, or Review). This classification was not used to generate narrative clusters but to describe how different types of studies contribute to the articulation of CSF narratives. Annex B provides a complete list of reviewed publications grouped by narrative cluster and source/mode classification.

Fig. 2. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram of the literature selection process.

4.4. Narrative clustering and synthesis

Following coding, publications were compared iteratively to identify points of convergence and divergence across the five analytical categories. Based on shared configurations of problem interpretations, actors, solutions, and future orientations, publications were grouped into thematic narrative clusters. The aim was not to force publications into mutually exclusive categories, but to identify recurring patterns through which the CSF concept was articulated across the literature. Clustering was guided by interpretive coherence within each articulation of the CSF concept rather than disciplinary origin, method, or publication year. Where publications contained substantial elements of more than one narrative configuration, overlap was acknowledged through assignment to more than one cluster. Emerging boundaries, cluster labels, and ambiguous cases were discussed with the second author during the analysis process. These discussions served as a validation step to check whether the proposed clusters were grounded in the coded material and consistently linked to the analytical dimensions.

To further support transparency, the final clusters were reviewed against the coding matrix and Annex B to ensure that each cluster reflected a recurring configuration across several publications rather than an isolated theme in a single text. The synthesis then connected these clusters back to the research questions.

4.5. Limitations

This review is limited to English-language publications and is predominantly based on European scholarship, which reflects the strong uptake and development of the CSF concept in the scientific literature. The inclusion of three EFI science-policy reports further reflects this European orientation. These reports were retained due to their formative role in articulating CSF as a European forest-sector concept, particularly in developing an integrated understanding of mitigation, adaptation, and the social dimension that was subsequently taken up in scientific publications. However, the review does not capture the full range of grey literature or practice-based accounts. Broader reports and grey literature addressing CSF in relation to the CSA and international development were not included in the coded literature database. Consequently, development-oriented interpretations and applications of CSF, particularly those emerging from lower- and middle-income regions, are less visible in the analysis.

In addition, as a thematic narrative review of scientific literature, the analysis provides a systematic synthesis of how the CSF concept is articulated within academic research. Other arenas in which CSF takes shape, particularly through collaborative, institutional, or place-based processes, are not directly examined here. Lastly, narrative analysis is inherently interpretive. Analytical decisions, including coding judgments and cluster boundaries, represent one systematic synthesis of the literature and do not constitute an exhaustive classification.

5. Results

5.1. Overview of the reviewed CSF literature

The final set of literature comprises 32 scientific publications that explicitly engage with CSF, published between 2015 and 2025. Across the reviewed literature, several publications focus on defining CSF in relation to European climate and forest policy contexts, with particular emphasis on mitigation objectives and the role of forests in achieving climate targets (e.g., Nabuurs et al., 2015; Nabuurs et al., 2018; Kauppi et al., 2018). Other publications address CSF through the development of evaluation tools, monitoring approaches, and management strategies (e.g., Alfieri et al., 2024; Mathys et al., 2021; Santopuoli et al., 2021). The set also includes national and regional case studies examining CSF implementation in specific contexts (e.g., Cienciala, 2022; Giongo et al., 2021; Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2022), as well as publications that engage

explicitly with social and governance aspects such as collective forest regimes and participatory processes (e.g., Brnkalakova et al., 2022; Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022).

Geographically, the reviewed literature is concentrated primarily in Europe. Of the 32 publications, 22 examine European countries or regions, including Sweden, Finland, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Austria, Spain, Italy, Ireland, the Czech Republic, and Turkey, as well as pan-European analyses. Four publications examine North American contexts (United States), one focuses on South America (Brazil), and one on Asia (China). An additional four adopt a global perspective. Collectively, the reviewed publications demonstrate a clear concentration in European and other high-income country contexts, with limited representation of studies from lower- and middle-income regions.

In terms of CSF pillars, the reviewed publications vary in how they address CSF. Most publications address mitigation and adaptation jointly ($n = 23$). A smaller number integrate the social dimensions alongside other pillars ($n = 3$) or address mitigation, adaptation, and social dimensions together ($n = 2$).

With regard to source/mode classification, the dataset includes conceptual, modeling, empirical, and review-based studies (see Annex B). Conceptual and empirical contributions constitute the largest share overall, while modeling studies form a distinct subset and review articles provide synthesis across strands. The distribution varies across clusters but was not used as a criterion in cluster construction.

5.2. CSF narrative clusters

The narrative analysis identified four thematic clusters that represent recurring patterns in how the CSF concept is articulated across the reviewed literature. Each cluster reveals a distinct configuration of problem interpretation, actors and agency, proposed solutions, envisioned futures, and the relative emphasis across the CSF pillars. For additional context, the actor categories discussed within these clusters are analytical, rather than mutually exclusive, as publications often assign overlapping roles to forest owners, farmers, community members, collective forest users, civil society organizations, and governance actors. The analysis therefore distinguishes actors according to the role attributed to them within each publication, such as agenda-setting, knowledge production, participatory governance, collective organization, land management, or implementation.

Fig. 3 synthesizes the defining characteristics of these clusters. Although analytically distinct, the clusters are not mutually exclusive, and individual publications may exhibit elements of more than one narrative. Annex B provides an overview of the publications associated with each cluster. It also indicates source/mode classifications and publications assigned to more than one cluster.

5.2.1. Narrative cluster A: CSF as a pathway to achieving climate goals

This cluster presents CSF as a means of aligning the forest sector more directly with climate mitigation objectives. It positions forests as underutilized yet scalable contributors to climate targets and decarbonization strategies.

Problem Interpretation.

Across this cluster, CSF is mobilized in response to perceived missed or constrained mitigation opportunities within existing climate and forest policy frameworks. Several contributions argue that forests' mitigation potential remains undervalued due to narrow accounting approaches that emphasize standing carbon stocks while overlooking substitution effects, harvested wood products, and long-term system dynamics (Nabuurs et al., 2015; Nabuurs et al., 2017). Others suggest that prevailing management and policy assumptions do not sufficiently demonstrate how mitigation outcomes could be optimized spatially or economically, or by species choice, even within established commercial forestry systems (Kauppi et al., 2018; Yousefpour et al., 2018; Shephard

Fig. 3. Synthesis of four narrative clusters identified in CSF literature. Clusters are analytically distinct but not mutually exclusive; individual publications may reflect elements of more than one cluster.

et al., 2022). More recent contributions further suggest that business-as-usual trajectories may not sustain current levels of forest carbon sequestration, which indicates the need to reorient management strategies to meet climate targets (Papa et al., 2023; Hetemäki and Verkerk, 2022).

Actors and Agency.

Agency is primarily attributed to policy and governance actors who shape climate target-setting, accounting rules, and incentive structures that determine what counts as mitigation and which management pathways are rewarded (Nabuurs et al., 2015; Nabuurs et al., 2017; Verkerk et al., 2020). Scientific and research actors support this governance agenda by quantifying mitigation potential through system-level assessments and modeling, including optimization of cost-efficient carbon sequestration and applied analyses of mitigation performance in production forestry contexts (Nabuurs et al., 2018; Yousefpour et al., 2018; Shephard et al., 2022). Forest managers and forest owners appear mainly as implementers whose practices are shaped by policy signals rather than as primary agenda-setters (Shephard et al., 2022; Hetemäki and Verkerk, 2022). Civil society and NGO actors are not explicitly positioned as central agents within this mitigation-oriented narrative.

Proposed solutions.

Proposed solutions emphasize restructuring forest management and forest-based value chains to maximize long-term mitigation outcomes. Common strategies mentioned include maintaining or expanding forest area, managing age-class distributions to sustain long-term carbon sinks, promoting long-lived wood products, and strengthening substitution effects through increased wood use in construction and materials (Nabuurs et al., 2015; Kauppi et al., 2018). Several papers stress the importance of regionally differentiated or portfolio-based management

approaches that balance carbon sequestration with economic performance and disturbance risks (Yousefpour et al., 2018; Papa et al., 2023), while others highlight intensified, yet climate-aligned, silvicultural practices within existing production systems (Shephard et al., 2022). Policy reform is consistently articulated as necessary to enable these practices, particularly through adjustments to accounting rules, incentives, and long-term planning frameworks (Nabuurs et al., 2017; Verkerk et al., 2020).

Envisioned Future.

The future envisioned across this cluster is one in which forests are fully integrated into climate mitigation portfolios and contribute predictably and at scale to emission reduction pathways. Forests are portrayed as dynamic mitigation assets that can simultaneously support timber production and bio-based value chains, provided that management and policy frameworks are aligned with long-term climate objectives (Nabuurs et al., 2018; Hetemäki and Verkerk, 2022; Papa et al., 2023).

CSF Pillar Emphasis.

Mitigation is the dominant CSF pillar in this cluster, with most contributions explicitly centering carbon sequestration and substitution as primary objectives (Nabuurs et al., 2015; Kauppi et al., 2018; Papa et al., 2023). Adaptation is also present, although largely instrumental and articulated as necessary to safeguard long-term mitigation performance under changing climatic conditions (Nabuurs et al., 2018; Shephard et al., 2022; Hetemäki and Verkerk, 2022). Lastly, the social dimensions pillar receives limited, indirect attention, typically appearing through references to policy alignment or economic incentives (Verkerk et al., 2020) rather than participatory or equity-oriented framings.

5.2.2. Narrative cluster B: CSF for resilience and multifunctionality

This cluster articulates CSF as a response to growing climate-related disturbances and ecological pressures, which emphasize the capacity of forests to sustain multiple functions under uncertainty. Across this cluster, CSF is presented as addressing the vulnerability of forest systems to drought, storms, pests, wildfire, and biodiversity decline, while maintaining mitigation as one objective among several interlinked management goals.

Problem Interpretation.

The central problem articulated in this cluster is the increasing exposure of forests to climate-induced disturbances that challenge existing management models and threaten long-term ecosystem functioning. Several studies point to drought stress, bark beetle outbreaks, and forest dieback as indicators that current forest structures and species compositions are misaligned with emerging climate conditions (Cienciala, 2022; Hanewinkel et al., 2022). Others emphasize wildfire risk, storms, and cascading disturbance regimes that simultaneously undermine carbon storage, timber supply, and ecosystem services (Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2022; Piazza et al., 2024). CSF, as such, is articulated as addressing trade-offs among mitigation, adaptation, and ecosystem services, rather than as a single-objective management rationale (Santopuoli et al., 2021; Peltola et al., 2022; Weatherall et al., 2022).

Actors and Agency.

Agency in this cluster is distributed across scientific and research actors, forest managers and owners, and policy and governance institutions. Scientific actors play a central role in diagnosing climate risks, developing indicators, and informing adaptive strategies (Mathys et al., 2021; Torresan et al., 2021; Weatherall et al., 2022). Forest managers and forest owners are positioned as key implementers of climate-adapted practices at stand and landscape scales, particularly in species selection, thinning regimes, and disturbance management (Peltola et al., 2022; Sikkema et al., 2024). Policy and governance actors, meanwhile, are presented as enabling adaptation through incentive schemes, harmonized monitoring frameworks, and governance reforms that support multifunctional outcomes instead of prescriptive targets alone (Brnkalakova et al., 2021; Santopuoli et al., 2021). Finally, civil society and NGO actors are not consistently foregrounded and remain largely implicit in this expert- and practitioner-driven resilience narrative.

Proposed solutions.

Proposed solutions in this cluster emphasize adaptive and multifunctional management portfolios. These include diversifying species composition, shifting from monoculture to mixed and climate-adapted stands, modifying rotation lengths, and applying continuous cover or close-to-nature forest management approaches (Hanewinkel et al., 2022; Peltola et al., 2022; Sikkema et al., 2024). Scenario-based studies also compare alternative management pathways, such as increased harvesting, reduced harvesting, bioenergy-oriented management, and wood-product-oriented strategies, to assess their implications for carbon storage, soil carbon, biomass stocks, and long-term climate benefits (Jandl et al., 2018). Several contributions underscore landscape-level interventions to reduce disturbance risks, such as fuel management, spatial planning, and coordinated fire and pest control (Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2022; Piazza et al., 2024). Others highlight the use of monitoring technologies, indicators, and national-scale assessment frameworks as tools for detecting disturbance impacts, informing adaptive responses, and managing trade-offs among carbon storage, biodiversity, and forest functions under changing climate conditions (Mathys et al., 2021; Torresan et al., 2021; Weatherall et al., 2022). Incentive-based instruments, including payments for ecosystem services (PES) and afforestation or restoration measures, are also presented as mechanisms to align adaptation, mitigation, and rural development (Brnkalakova et al., 2021; Stavi et al., 2024).

Envisioned Future.

The envisioned future across this cluster is one of resilient, multifunctional forest landscapes capable of sustaining ecosystem services, supporting economic activities, and contributing to climate mitigation under persistent disturbance and uncertainty (Santopuoli et al., 2021; Peltola et al., 2022; Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2022; Hanewinkel et al., 2022). Forests are depicted as adaptive socio-ecological systems that balance carbon storage, biodiversity, timber production, and protective functions, rather than as narrowly optimized mitigation infrastructures (Mathys et al., 2021; Weatherall et al., 2022; Sikkema et al., 2024). Several studies articulate futures characterized by continuous monitoring, adaptive management cycles, and stronger integration of forests into regional and national climate strategies (Santopuoli et al., 2021; Torresan et al., 2021; Hanewinkel et al., 2022).

CSF Pillar Emphasis.

This cluster places strong emphasis on adaptation and ecosystem resilience, while maintaining mitigation as an integrated but not dominant pillar (Cienciala, 2022; Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2022; Peltola et al., 2022). Carbon sequestration is treated alongside biodiversity conservation, risk reduction, and the maintenance of multiple ecosystem services (Jandl et al., 2018; Mathys et al., 2021; Weatherall et al., 2022; Stavi et al., 2024). The social dimensions pillar manifests primarily through governance arrangements, incentive mechanisms, and the role of forest owners and managers in implementing adaptive practices (Brnkalakova et al., 2021; Sikkema et al., 2024; Hanewinkel et al., 2022), with limited emphasis on explicit participatory or equity-focused interpretations.

5.2.3. Narrative cluster C: CSF as modernization and operationalization

This cluster presents CSF as a reform-oriented means to modernize forest management by translating integrated climate objectives into operational practices, metrics, and technologies. Across the literature, CSF is articulated as a concept oriented towards operationalization, intended to bridge the gap between high-level climate ambitions and on-the-ground decision-making by embedding adaptation and mitigation goals into measurable, technology-supported management systems.

Problem Interpretation.

The core problem defined in this cluster is the limited operationalization of the CSF concept within existing forest management and policy frameworks. Several contributions identify a mismatch between integrated CSF ambitions and fragmented management practices that remain oriented towards single objectives or lack robust monitoring and implementation tools (Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023; Santopuoli et al., 2021). Climate change is presented as intensifying risks and uncertainty, particularly in disturbance-prone, regionally sensitive forest systems, while current instruments are seen as insufficient to support adaptive, evidence-based responses under these conditions (Alfieri et al., 2024; Torresan et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024).

Actors and Agency.

Agency is primarily attributed to scientific and research actors, together with policy and governance institutions, who are positioned as responsible for developing and deploying operational tools aligned with CSF objectives. Scientific actors are tasked with designing indicators, monitoring systems, and assessment frameworks that translate CSF objectives into actionable guidance (Bowditch et al., 2020; Santopuoli et al., 2021). In addition, policy and governance actors are portrayed as responsible for aligning strategies, legislation, and forest management plans with CSF criteria and identifying institutional reform needs through indicator-based assessments (Gençay and Birben, 2024). Forest managers, forest owners, and practitioners are presented mainly as recipients and users of reformed management instruments and incentive structures (Chizmar et al., 2025). Civil society and NGO actors appear as supporting contributors, particularly in monitoring, engagement, and implementation (Chizmar et al., 2025).

Proposed Solutions.

Proposed solutions center on deploying tools that support integrated and adaptive management. These include shared indicator sets for CSF and harmonized data systems (Santopuoli et al., 2021), advanced monitoring technologies such as remote sensing and sensor networks (Torresan et al., 2021), and digital decision-support systems that integrate artificial intelligence (AI), LiDAR, digital twins, and IoT-based data streams to assess forest condition, support scenario-based planning, and optimize management interventions under climate uncertainty (Wang et al., 2024). Composite assessment indices and adaptive silvicultural practices further translate CSF objectives into management-relevant guidance that enables the balancing of carbon, biodiversity, productivity, and risk considerations in practice (Peltola et al., 2022; Alfieri et al., 2024). Policy reforms and incentive mechanisms aligned with CSF goals are also highlighted as necessary to support uptake and implementation (Gençay and Birben, 2024; Chizmar et al., 2025).

Envisioned Future.

The envisioned future is one of climate-resilient and multifunctional forests managed through continuous monitoring, adaptive decision-making, and anticipatory planning. Forest systems are expected to sustain ecosystem services, contribute to mitigation through carbon storage and substitution, and remain economically viable under changing climatic conditions (Peltola et al., 2022). CSF-enabled management is portrayed as increasingly data-informed and institutionally embedded, supported by indicator-based governance and periodic updating of policies and management plans to maintain alignment with evolving climate conditions and CSF objectives (Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023; Gençay and Birben, 2024; Wang et al., 2024).

CSF Pillar Emphasis.

Mitigation and adaptation are jointly emphasized across the cluster, with mitigation linked to carbon sequestration and substitution benefits and adaptation linked to resilience, disturbance response, and adaptive capacity (Santopuoli et al., 2021; Peltola et al., 2022; Chizmar et al., 2025). The social dimensions pillar is also present but secondary, mainly through references to stakeholder engagement, incentive mechanisms, and implementation support that facilitate the uptake of modernized, climate-responsive forest management practices (Bowditch et al., 2020; Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023; Chizmar et al., 2025).

5.2.4. Narrative cluster D: CSF for socio-economic, governance, and collective transformation

This cluster presents CSF as a transformative governance and socio-economic undertaking in which climate objectives are closely linked to institutional change, collective action, and social sustainability. Across the included studies, CSF is articulated as a concept that connects climate goals with reforms in policy design, participatory decision-making, and cross-sector and cross-scale coordination. In addition, forests are positioned as socio-ecological systems embedded in broader development trajectories shaped by governance arrangements and collective capacities.

Problem Interpretation.

The central problem described in this cluster is the misalignment between the prevailing forest governance arrangements and the interconnected challenges of climate change, rural development, and social well-being. Several studies identify fragmented policy frameworks, centralized or sectorally bounded decision-making, and limited integration of social considerations as constraints on effective climate-smart action (Dubova et al., 2022; Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022). Others emphasize structural vulnerabilities linked to deforestation pressures, market dynamics, and uneven institutional capacity, particularly in contexts where climate objectives intersect with socio-economic priorities (Giongo et al., 2021). CSF is thus articulated as addressing systemic governance and socio-economic limitations alongside ecological risk.

Actors and Agency.

Agency is distributed across multiple actor groups operating at different levels. Policy and governance institutions play a central role in shaping regulatory frameworks, incentives, and strategic orientations for CSF (Dubova et al., 2022; Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023). Civil society organizations, NGO actors, and place-based community actors are positioned as active participants in participatory governance, collective management, and implementation processes (Brnkakalova et al., 2022; Giongo et al., 2021). Here, place-based community actors refer to residents, community groups, collective forest users, or local associations involved in or affected by forest governance; depending on the publication, these categories may overlap with forest owners or farmers. In some cases, collective forestry regimes are described as socially innovative arrangements, in which self-organization, shared rules, and participation enable new forms of governance aligned with CSF objectives (Brnkakalova et al., 2022). Scientific and research actors contribute knowledge, analytical tools, and conceptual clarification that inform governance reform and coordination (Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022). Forest managers, forest owners, farmers, and industry actors appear primarily as implementers whose practices are shaped by evolving institutional contexts, including incentive-based schemes and policy instruments (Brnkakalova et al., 2021).

Proposed solutions.

Proposed solutions emphasize innovations in governance and collective mechanisms that integrate climate, social, and economic objectives. These include policy mixes combining regulatory instruments with incentive-based approaches such as certification schemes, PES, and climate-related financial mechanisms (Dubova et al., 2022; Giongo et al., 2021). Capacity building, stakeholder participation, and collective management arrangements are highlighted as practices supporting social learning, legitimacy, and adaptive governance (Brnkakalova et al., 2022; Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022). Case-based contributions illustrate how incentive structures and participatory design can support CSF implementation by aligning climate objectives with local socio-economic conditions, without advancing broader claims of systemic governance transformation (Brnkakalova et al., 2021). Several studies also highlight the role of institutional coordination and multi-level governance in aligning forest management with broader sustainability and climate goals (Brnkakalova et al., 2022; Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023).

Envisioned Future.

The envisioned future centers on forest systems that support climate mitigation and adaptation while contributing to resilient economies and socially inclusive development pathways. Forests are embedded within collaborative governance structures that balance ecological functions with livelihood security and social equity (Brnkakalova et al., 2022; Dubova et al., 2022). This future emphasizes empowered communities, diversified rural development trajectories, and governance systems capable of coordinating across sectors and scales in response to climate challenges (Giongo et al., 2021; Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023).

CSF Pillar Emphasis.

The social dimensions pillar is prominent in this cluster, closely intertwined with adaptation, and to a lesser extent, mitigation. Social dimensions such as participation, governance, equity, and collective capacity are foregrounded as foundational conditions for climate-smart outcomes (Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022; Brnkakalova et al., 2022). Adaptation is addressed through institutional flexibility and collective responsiveness to change, while mitigation is integrated within broader socio-economic and governance strategies (Dubova et al., 2022; Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023).

6. Discussion

This review shows that CSF is not a single, clearly defined framework but a flexible climate-oriented concept structured through recurring

narrative configurations. Across the reviewed literature, mitigation and adaptation provide a relatively stable conceptual core, while the social dimension remains relatively less consistently specified. This combination of coherence and variation matters because it shapes which problems, actors, forms of knowledge, and pathways of change become visible in CSF research and policy debates. The following discussion interprets these patterns in relation to the three research questions: how CSF is conceptualized, where these conceptualizations converge and diverge, and what governance implications arise from these patterns.

6.1. CSF as a flexible but unevenly integrated climate concept

CSF is conceptualized in the reviewed scientific literature as an integrative but non-uniform concept linking mitigation, adaptation, and the social dimension without prescribing a single pathway. This flexibility helps explain its appeal across scientific and policy contexts, as it accommodates carbon-oriented, resilience-oriented, operational, and governance-oriented interpretations. Similar dynamics have been observed in other broad sustainability concepts, such as CSA and the circular economy, where integrative concepts bring heterogeneous objectives and perspectives together while also generating ambiguity, divergent interpretations, and uneven attention to social, environmental, technical, and political dimensions (Chandra et al., 2018; Leipold et al., 2023).

Despite this variation, CSF has a recognizable conceptual core. Mitigation is expressed through carbon sequestration, substitution effects, harvested wood products, and forest-sector contributions to climate targets, while adaptation is expressed through resilience, disturbance risk reduction, adaptive management, and the maintenance of forest functions under climate uncertainty. The social dimension, however, is less consistently developed. In some conceptualizations, it is elaborated through governance arrangements, stakeholder engagement, collective management, and institutional coordination. In others, it appears more instrumentally through economic incentives, implementation capacity, employment, regional development, or public acceptability. Collectively, CSF appears integrative in principle but unevenly elaborated in practice, particularly where questions of participation, equity, institutional conditions, power, and distribution remain more variably addressed.

This unevenness is also reflected in the source and mode of knowledge production (Annex B). Conceptual and modeling studies often stabilize mitigation-oriented understandings of CSF through carbon accounting, scenario analysis, and system-level optimization. Empirical studies more often extend the concept towards ecological uncertainty, adaptive management, governance arrangements, and collective processes. Review studies synthesize integrative formulations, but do not consistently deepen the social dimensions pillar. As such, the uneven development of CSF reflects not only conceptual ambiguity, but also how different types of studies make particular aspects of CSF more visible than others.

This finding is consistent with the policy origins of much of the reviewed literature. Foundational European contributions developed CSF in response to debates on how forests and the forest sector could contribute to post-2020 climate targets, particularly through forest sinks, substitution effects, LULUCF accounting, and regionally differentiated policy incentives (Nabuurs et al., 2015; Nabuurs et al., 2017; Hetemäki and Verkerk, 2022). Hetemäki and Verkerk (2022) also note that the FAO had used CSF language earlier within the broader CSA agenda, primarily in relation to developing-country contexts. However, in the selected forestry literature reviewed here, CSF is most concretely articulated through European climate and forest policy debates, where attention centers on the measurable contribution of forests to climate targets and the management, accounting, and policy mechanisms required to achieve them.

Weatherall et al. (2022) trace the early development of CSF to a mitigation-oriented understanding of forestry and acknowledge that,

although the social dimension was subsequently introduced as a core pillar, it still requires greater attention. Bowditch et al. (2020) similarly recognize the social dimension within CSF, but much of its operationalization concerns stakeholder coordination, institutional and technical capacities, knowledge exchange, public acceptance, and other conditions needed to implement climate-oriented forest management. Hallberg-Sramek et al. (2022) further show that established CSF indicator sets primarily captured environmental characteristics and forest conditions, while local stakeholders brought forward additional social concerns, including employment, ownership, taxation, local value chains, knowledge, and collaboration. Cooper and MacFarlane (2023) likewise identify risks that the current CSF may overlook smaller land-owners and Indigenous and rural communities, reproduce unequal benefit distribution, and create technical barriers to participation. These studies altogether help explain why the social dimension is often acknowledged within CSF, but is more consistently articulated through implementation feasibility, stakeholder coordination, and public acceptance than through inclusion, safeguards, power relations, or benefit distribution.

6.2. Patterns of convergence and divergence across CSF narratives

Across all narrative clusters, CSF conceptualizations converge around a shared climate-oriented problem interpretation. Climate change is consistently understood as a systemic and long-term challenge marked by increasing disturbance regimes, uncertainty, and risk, requiring anticipatory and coordinated responses in forest systems. This shared problem horizon gives CSF a clear climate-centered orientation and also helps explain why mitigation and adaptation remain core pillars across the reviewed literature. However, the narratives diverge in how this problem is translated into action, ranging from carbon optimization and forest-sector contributions to climate targets, to resilience, multifunctionality, monitoring tools, governance coordination, and socio-economic transformation. These differences indicate shifts in analytical emphasis rather than conceptual fragmentation.

The social dimension constitutes the clearest point of divergence across the narratives. Although it is formally recognized alongside mitigation and adaptation (Bowditch et al., 2020; Weatherall et al., 2022), it is elaborated unevenly across the reviewed literature. In mitigation-centered and operationalization narratives, social dimensions are often articulated through economic efficiency, employment, implementation feasibility, or public acceptability. In governance-oriented narratives, they extend towards stakeholder engagement, institutional reform, and collective learning. Related research also underscores the importance of awareness and social acceptance for climate-oriented forest strategies (Laakkonen et al., 2018) and calls for stronger integration of social dimensions in sustainability-oriented forest management (Scheffers et al., 2016). Yet distributional implications and differentiated social impacts remain weakly specified, consistent with other observations in CSA studies (Karlsson et al., 2017).

This unevenness is also visible in how actors and agency are represented. While the reviewed literature refers to stakeholders, communities, forest managers and forest owners, farmers, civil society and NGO actors, and policy and governance actors, these groups are often treated as broad or overlapping categories rather than as socially differentiated actors with distinct interests, capacities, and decision-making power. Policy and governance actors are consistently positioned as central agents, whereas scientific and research actors are prominent in publications focused on carbon accounting, modeling, indicators, decision-support tools, and monitoring systems. Forest managers, forest owners, and farmers are often presented as implementers of management practices or incentive schemes, while place-based community actors and civil society and NGO actors are more often articulated as participants in consultation, collective governance, or local implementation processes. These categories are not mutually exclusive, particularly in rural or collective forestry contexts where ownership,

livelihood, residence, and community membership may overlap. However, the limited differentiation between them makes it difficult to assess who is expected to participate in, implement, benefit from, or bear the costs of CSF interventions.

The divergence therefore concerns not only whether the social dimension is included, but also how concretely actor roles, forms of agency, and social consequences are specified within CSF narratives (Wittmayer et al., 2019). Participation, implementation, and governance are not interchangeable forms of agency. More explicit attention to actor differentiation would help clarify how responsibilities, benefits, risks, and decision-making authority are distributed across CSF strategies. It would also make visible the power-related concerns that shape whether CSF can support socially inclusive and legitimate forest governance. Even where governance-oriented narratives emphasize participation and collective arrangements, attention to power asymmetries, value pluralities, and differentiated experiences remains limited, reflecting broader tendencies in forest policy research (Arts et al., 2010; Winkel, 2012).

These divergences point to recurrent tensions that remain only partly articulated in the reviewed literature. Although CSF is often presented as an integrative concept, the literature does not always make explicit how competing objectives should be balanced in practice. The identified narrative configurations suggest trade-offs between carbon optimization and adaptive resilience, between mitigation performance and timber production objectives, between bioeconomy expansion and biodiversity conservation, and between standardized implementation frameworks and context-specific livelihood outcomes. Certain forest uses and values, such as non-timber forest products or subsistence-oriented practices, are less frequently positioned as central within dominant narratives. Biodiversity is commonly referenced, although it is often treated as a co-benefit or contextual consideration rather than as a primary organizing objective (e.g., Mathys et al., 2021; Torresan et al., 2021). Emerging formulations that integrate biodiversity objectives, such as climate- and biodiversity-smart forestry (Feliciano et al., 2024), and publications that extend CSF beyond European contexts (Wang et al., 2024), illustrate the adaptability of the concept. However, this adaptability also reinforces the need to specify which objectives are prioritized, by whom, and with what consequences in particular contexts. Without such clarification, the balancing of mitigation, adaptation, biodiversity, production, and socio-economic objectives risks remaining implicit rather than openly examined.

6.3. Governance implications of CSF narrative patterns

The identified narrative patterns have direct implications for how CSF is interpreted and operationalized in governance contexts. First, they suggest that CSF is shaped by broader processes of climatization in forest governance, where forests are increasingly articulated through their role in climate mitigation, carbon dynamics, and climate policy targets (Singer and Giessen, 2017; Pülzl et al., 2024). The consequence is not the absence of adaptation, biodiversity, or the social dimension, but their frequent organization around a climate-centered policy logic. In this context, CSF can help integrate climate objectives into forest governance, but it can also risk privileging aggregate climate performance over distributional and power-related concerns.

Second, the geographically uneven evidence base also shapes how CSF is conceptualized. Although the reviewed publications include cases beyond Europe, including Brazil and China, the literature remains predominantly concentrated in European and other high-income country contexts. Recent bibliometric analysis likewise indicates a strong concentration of CSF research in high-income regions and more limited representation from lower- and middle-income regions (Alawode et al., 2026). Given the European policy origins discussed above, this concentration suggests that dominant CSF narratives are shaped by contexts where climate policy, carbon accounting, LULUCF rules, bioeconomy strategies, and institutional implementation capacity are central

concerns. This raises questions about whether current conceptualizations of CSF are sufficiently robust across governance contexts where forest-climate challenges are organized around different priorities.

This geographical unevenness also raises questions about transferability. The issue is not that CSF cannot travel across contexts, but that its current evidence base provides limited insight into how the concept is interpreted and contested under different policy and socio-economic conditions. That said, if CSF is largely elaborated through European policy concerns, its dominant narratives may not fully capture forest-climate challenges in lower- and middle-income regions, where land tenure, livelihood dependence, customary forest use, Indigenous and local knowledge, state capacity, restoration agendas, or development priorities may be more central. Comparable work on agroforestry extension illustrates a broader transferability issue: approaches developed in one region often require adaptation to local tenure conditions, farmer decision-making capacities, community networks, and institutional support systems (Reid, 2017). More comparative research is therefore needed to examine whether and how CSF narratives evolve in regions where forest-climate policy is framed less through LULUCF accounting and bioeconomy strategies, and more through adaptation, development, land rights, restoration, community-based or livelihood-oriented forest governance.

Third, the concentration of agency in institutional and expert domains has consequences for how CSF problems and solutions are defined. Across the reviewed literature, policy and governance actors, scientific and research actors, forest managers and forest owners, and modeling, monitoring, and decision-support systems are central to the articulation of CSF. These actors and systems are important for implementation, but their prominence may narrow the forms of knowledge and experience that shape CSF strategies. This pattern also reflects wider inequalities in global knowledge production, where research capacity, agenda-setting authority, and publication visibility remain unevenly distributed across regions (Masood, 2018; Van Noorden et al., 2014). Wider environmental governance research has shown that local, Indigenous, and experiential knowledge systems are often marginalized in global and national environmental policy debates (Beymer-Farris and Bassett, 2012; Martin et al., 2013; Dawson et al., 2018). Applied to CSF, this suggests the need to examine not only which practices are promoted, but also whose knowledge, values, and priorities are included in defining climate-smart forest futures.

These patterns can be read alongside established forest governance discourses, without treating the CSF narrative clusters as direct equivalents of those discourses. The mitigation-oriented cluster most closely aligns with the *Forests and Climate Change* discourse, which positions forests as instruments for climate mitigation and adaptation within international and policy-oriented forest governance debates (McDermott, 2014; Buizer et al., 2014; Pülzl et al., 2024). The resilience and multifunctionality cluster overlaps with sustainable forest management and ecological limits discourses, given its emphasis on multifunctional landscapes, adaptation, and ecological uncertainty (Arts et al., 2010; Pülzl et al., 2024). The operationalization cluster echoes elements of ecological modernization and bioeconomy thinking, especially through its focus on indicators, monitoring, efficiency, innovation, and implementation capacity (Kleinschmit et al., 2009; Kleinschmit et al., 2014; Ramcilovic-Suominen and Pülzl, 2018; Pülzl et al., 2024). The governance-oriented cluster is closest to civic environmentalism and environmental justice orientations, which foreground participation, institutional reform, power, and the inclusion of diverse actors and knowledge systems (Winkel, 2012; Newell et al., 2021; Pülzl et al., 2024). This comparison situates the identified CSF narratives within longer-standing forest governance debates about who defines forest futures, which objectives are prioritized, and whose knowledge and interests are recognized, without treating the clusters as direct equivalents of those discourses.

By and large, these findings suggest the need for more reflexive approaches to the development and application of the CSF concept in

research and governance. Conceptual flexibility can be productive when it enables adaptation to regional contexts and supports dialogue across policy objectives. However, it can also conceal unresolved tensions if trade-offs, actor roles, and social consequences are not made explicit. This concern is also reflected in research on CSA, where context, scale, and political ideologies shape how climate-smart approaches are interpreted, and where flexibility needs to be accompanied by attention to trade-offs, synergies, and broad social participation (Chandra et al., 2018).

Co-design and knowledge co-production may help address these concerns by creating spaces where problem definitions, evaluation criteria, and competing interpretations can be more openly deliberated (Miller and Wyborn, 2020; Norström et al., 2020; Kerr et al., 2023). Dialogue-oriented and reflexive learning formats (e.g., Leipold et al., 2024) can play an important role in making CSF assumptions, trade-offs, and exclusions discussable among researchers, practitioners, policy actors, and place-based stakeholders. Related research further indicates that wider participation, including place-based and experiential forms of knowledge, can broaden how sustainability-related problems are interpreted and understood (Huttunen et al., 2022; Muhr, 2020; Muhr et al., 2024). Within such processes, making alternative CSF narratives more visible may strengthen science-policy interaction by bringing competing problem interpretations, assumptions, and governance priorities into dialogue (Leipold et al., 2024). This may reduce the risk that CSF becomes a technical label for climate performance alone. A more reflexive CSF agenda would therefore explicitly examine how mitigation, adaptation, and the social dimension are prioritized, negotiated, and experienced across different governance contexts.

7. Conclusion

This review identifies four recurring narrative clusters through which CSF is interpreted in the selected scientific literature: CSF as a pathway to achieving climate goals, CSF for resilience and multifunctionality, CSF as modernization and operationalization, and CSF for socio-economic, governance, and collective transformation. The analysis shows that CSF is not articulated as a single and stable framework across the literature, but is shaped through patterned narrative configurations that influence how climate-related forest challenges are defined, how mitigation, adaptation, and the social dimension are prioritized, and how responsibility for climate-oriented forest strategies is assigned. Its coherence lies mainly in the shared emphasis on mitigation and adaptation, while divergence emerges in the treatment of the social dimension, actor roles, and implementation pathways. Similar to CSA, CSF is often presented as an integrative approach, but integration does not occur evenly across its pillars (Chandra et al., 2018). The inclusion of CSF pillar emphasis as a fifth analytical category made this unevenness visible by showing how the three pillars are combined, prioritized, or marginalized across different narrative clusters.

A key implication is that CSF research needs more careful articulation of stakeholder roles, power relations, and distributional questions. Across the reviewed literature, policy and governance actors are frequently positioned as central, while forest owners, managers, communities, civil society actors, and other place-based stakeholders are often assigned narrower roles as implementers, beneficiaries, or participants. CSF therefore raises not only technical questions about combining mitigation and adaptation measures, but also questions about who defines forest-climate priorities, bears implementation costs and risks, benefits from proposed strategies, and whose knowledge counts in decision-making. More explicit attention to land tenure, livelihoods, safeguards, benefit distribution, and differentiated responsibilities would strengthen the social dimension of CSF and help avoid treating participation as an add-on to technical or policy-led approaches. This is particularly important where CSF is articulated through production and forest-sector performance, because such interpretations tend to give less visibility to distributional effects and to

the roles of smaller landholders, Indigenous communities, and rural communities (Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023).

CSF should also be understood in relation to adjacent and partly overlapping forest and sustainability concepts, including sustainable forest management, forest and landscape restoration, and climate-resilient forestry. Rather than replacing these concepts, CSF co-evolves with them and selectively draws on their vocabularies. Some issues that appear underdeveloped in the CSF literature, including participation, equity, land tenure, livelihood dependence, and community-based governance, may therefore be addressed more extensively under adjacent concepts. The limited specification of the social dimension in CSF should consequently be understood as a gap in CSF-labelled literature, not as evidence that participation, equity, land tenure, livelihoods or community-based approaches are absent from forest governance scholarship more broadly.

Recognizing the recurring CSF narrative configurations can support more reflexive science-policy interaction by making their underlying assumptions, trade-offs, and exclusions more visible. This aligns with calls for narrative-based approaches that help recognize, analyze, and engage with the values and paradigms shaping sustainability research and collaboration (Leipold et al., 2024). The contribution of narrative analysis is to show that unevenness within CSF research is produced not only by differences in thematic coverage or publication patterns, but also by how problems, actors, solutions, futures, and pillars are connected. Making these relationships explicit can support more transparent forest governance and reduce the risk that CSF becomes a technical label for climate performance.

As noted in the Methods, the review is based on a selected English-language dataset of scientific publications and a small number of formative science-policy reports. Broader grey literature and non-English scholarship are therefore not fully represented. The narrative analysis is also interpretive, and cluster boundaries may be drawn differently by other researchers. Future studies could examine how CSF is used in policy and practitioner materials, analyze its uptake beyond the European and other high-income country contexts that dominate the dataset, and explore how local actors interpret CSF in practice. Such work could also assess how land tenure, safeguards, biodiversity, community rights, and benefit distribution are addressed across different regional and governance conditions.

The scientific value of CSF lies not only in integrating mitigation and adaptation, but also in opening debate about what climate-oriented forestry should prioritize, whose knowledge and responsibilities are recognized, and how forest futures are imagined. CSF research and practice should therefore engage more explicitly with what particular narratives make visible, what they leave implicit, and what they may exclude. Future research using participatory, creative, and visual approaches offers a way to deepen this understanding by examining how local actors interpret CSF in practice, including how they understand forest change, management interventions, risks, responsibilities, and desired forest futures.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly for grammar, spelling, and language clarity, and ChatGPT for sentence-level paraphrasing and language refinement. The authors reviewed and edited the output as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Elaine Anne Parlade: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gerhard Weiss:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Funding

This work was conducted in the context of the Horizon Europe Project FORWARDS under grant agreement ID: 101084481. Open access funding provided by BOKU University.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have nothing to declare.

Appendix A. Example coding matrix illustrating the application of the narrative analysis framework on selected CSF papers

	Nabuurs et al., 2017	Mathys et al., 2021	Santopuoli et al., 2021	Brnkalakova et al., 2022
Problem Interpretation	Insufficient forest contribution to mitigation targets	Climate-related risks and uncertainty threaten multiple forest functions	Fragmented and inefficient forest management under climate change	Limited integration of social, economic, and governance dimensions in CSF
Key Actors	Policy and Governance Scientific and Research Forest Managers and Owners	Forest Managers and Owners Scientific and Research Policy and Governance	Scientific and Research Policy and Governance Forest Managers and Owners	Policy and Governance Civil Society and NGOs Scientific and Research
Proposed Solutions	Climate-oriented forest management strategies	Adaptive management balancing multiple objectives	Tools, indicators, operational guidance	Governance innovation and stakeholder coordination
Envisioned Future	Forest optimized for mitigation commitments	Resilient, multifunctional forest ecosystems	Modernized, data-driven forest management	Collectively steered CSF aligned with societal goals
CSF Pillar Emphasized	Mitigation	Adaptation	Mitigation, Adaptation	Social Dimension, Adaptation
Narrative Cluster (s)	A – Pathway to Achieving Climate Goals	B – Resilience and Multifunctionality	C – Modernization and Operationalization B – Resilience and Multifunctionality	D – Socio-Economic, Governance and Collective Transformation

Note: This matrix is illustrative and demonstrates how narrative clusters are derived from coded elements.

Appendix B. List of reviewed CSF publications grouped by Narrative Cluster and Source/Mode Classification

Legend (Source/Mode Classification): Conceptual (C); Modeling (M); Empirical (E); Review (R).

Cluster A: CSF as Pathway to Achieving Climate Goals	Cluster B: CSF for Resilience and Multifunctionality	Cluster C: CSF as Modernization and Operationalization	Cluster D: CSF for Socio-economic, Governance, and Collective Transformation
Hetemäki and Verkerk, 2022 (C) Kauppi et al., 2018 (C) Nabuurs et al., 2015 (C) Nabuurs et al., 2017 (M) Nabuurs et al., 2018 (C) Papa et al., 2023 (M) Shephard et al., 2022 (R) Verkerk et al., 2020 (C) Yousefpour et al., 2018 (M)	Brnkalakova et al., 2021 (E) Cienciala, 2022 (E) Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2022 (E) Hanewinkel et al., 2022 (M) Jandl et al., 2018 (M) Kauppi et al., 2018 (C) Mathys et al., 2021 (E) Peltola et al., 2022 (E) Piazza et al., 2024 (M) Santopuoli et al., 2021 (E) Sikkema et al., 2024 (E) Stavi et al., 2024 (R) Torresan et al., 2021 (M) Weatherall et al., 2022 (C)	Alfieri et al., 2024 (E) Bowditch et al., 2020 (C) Chizmar et al., 2025 (R) Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023 (R) Gençay and Birben, 2024 (C) Peltola et al., 2022 (E) Santopuoli et al., 2021 (E) Torresan et al., 2021 (M) Wang et al., 2024 (C)	Brnkalakova et al., 2021 (E) Brnkalakova et al., 2022 (E) Cooper and MacFarlane, 2023 (R) Dubova et al., 2022 (R) Giongo et al., 2021 (E) Hallberg-Sramek et al., 2022 (E)

Note: This annex lists all 32 reviewed CSF publications, their primary source/mode classification, and their assigned narrative cluster(s). Cluster assignment was based on the dominant narrative configuration identified in each publication. Publications containing substantial elements of more than one configuration were assigned to multiple clusters. Source/mode classification was used descriptively and did not determine cluster assignment.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

Alawode, G.L., Oluwajuwon, T.V., Adegbola, F.O., Oyefara, A.O., Daniel, O.I., 2026. Climate-smart forestry: a review of research trends and implementation approaches. *Mitig. Adapt. Strateg. Glob. Chang.* 31, 19.

Alfieri, D., Tognetti, R., Santopuoli, G., 2024. Exploring climate-smart forestry in Mediterranean forests through an innovative composite climate-smart index. *J. Environ. Manag.* 368, 122002.

Arts, B., Appelstrand, M., Kleinschmit, D., Püzl, H., Vissere-Hamakers, I., Atyi, R., Enters, T., McGinley, K., Yasmi, Y., 2010. Discourses, actors and instruments in international forest governance. In: *Embracing Complexity: Meeting the Challenges of IFG*. IUFRO World Series, vol. 28. Vienna.

Beymer-Farris, B.A., Bassett, T.J., 2012. The REDD menace: resurgent protectionism in Tanzania’s mangrove forests. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 22 (2), 332–341.

Bowditch, E., Santopuoli, G., Binder, F., Del Rio, M., La Porta, N., Kluvankova, T., Tognetti, R., 2020. What is climate-smart forestry? A definition from a multinational collaborative process focused on mountain regions of Europe. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 43, 101113.

- Brnkalkova, S., Světlík, J., Brynleifsdóttir, S.J., Snorrason, A., Baštáková, V., Klůvankova, T., 2021. Afforesting Icelandic land: A promising approach for climate-smart forestry? *Can. J. For. Res.* 51 (12), 1781–1790.
- Brnkalkova, S., Melnykovich, M., Nijnik, M., Barlagne, C., Pavelka, M., Udovc, A., Klůvanková, T., 2022. Collective forestry regimes to enhance transition to climate smart forestry. *Environ. Policy Gov.* 32 (6), 492–503.
- Buizer, M., Humphreys, D., de Jong, W., 2014. Climate change and deforestation: the evolution of an intersecting policy domain. *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 35, 1–11.
- Chandra, A., McNamara, K.E., Dargusch, P., 2018. Climate-smart agriculture: perspectives and framings. *Clim. Pol.* 18 (4), 526–541.
- Chizmar, S., Cushing, T., Baral, S., Ruseva, T., 2025. How do landowners perceive and respond to incentives for sustainable forest management? A synthesis to inform discussions on programs for climate-smart forestry. *Trees, Forests and People* 19, 100753.
- Cienciala, E., 2022. Climate-smart forestry case study: Czech Republic. In: *Forest Bioeconomy and Climate Change*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 173–182.
- Cooper, L., MacFarlane, D., 2023. Climate-smart forestry: promise and risks for forests, society, and climate. *Plos Climate* 2 (6), e0000212.
- Dawson, N.M., Mason, M., Fisher, J.A., Mwayafu, D.M., Dhungana, H., Schroeder, H., Zeitoun, M., 2018. Norm entrepreneurs sidestep REDD+ in pursuit of just and sustainable forest governance. *Sustainability* 10 (6), 1726.
- Dixon, R.K., Solomon, A.M., Brown, S., Houghton, R.A., Trexler, M.C., Wisniewski, J., 1994. Carbon pools and flux of global forest ecosystems. *Science* 263 (5144), 185–190.
- Dubova, L., Slavikova, L., Azevedo, J.C., Barstad, J., Gatto, P., Lesinski, J., Stokken, R., 2022. Review of policy instruments for climate-smart mountain forestry. In: *Climate-Smart Forestry in Mountain Regions*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 477–506.
- European Commission, 2019. *Communication from the Commission: The European Green Deal (COM/2019/640 Final)*. European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640>.
- European Commission, 2021. *New EU forest strategy for 2030*. European Union. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/forest-strategy_en.
- Feliciano, D., Schelhaas, M.-J., Starcevic, A., Staritsky, I., Uzquiano, S., Boonen, S., et al., 2024. D1.1 Forest management approaches across Europe. *FORESTPATHs*.
- Fischer, F., Forester, J. (Eds.), 1993. *The Argumentative Turn in Policy Analysis and Planning*. Duke University Press.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), 2013. *Climate-Smart Agriculture Sourcebook*. FAO.
- Gençay, G., Birben, Ü., 2024. Striving for sustainability: climate-smart forestry measures in Türkiye. *Int. For. Rev.* 26 (2), 198–211.
- Giongo, M., Santos, M.M., Da Silva, D.B., Cachoeira, J.N., Santopuoli, G., 2021. Climate-smart forestry in Brazil. In: *Climate-Smart Forestry in Mountain Regions*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 545–570.
- Góriz-Mifsud, E., Ameztegui, A., González, J.R., Trasobares, A., 2022. Climate-smart forestry case study: Spain. In: *Forest Bioeconomy and Climate Change*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 211–228.
- Hajer, M.A., 1995. *The Politics of Environmental Discourse: Ecological Modernization and the Policy Process*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Hallberg-Sramek, I., Reimerson, E., Priebe, J., Nordström, E.M., Mårdal, E., Sandström, C., Nordin, A., 2022. Bringing “climate-smart forestry” down to the local level—identifying barriers, pathways and indicators for its implementation in practice. *Forests* 13 (1), 98.
- Hanewinkel, M., Lessa Derci Augustynczyk, A., Yousefipour, R., 2022. Climate-smart forestry case study: Germany. In: *Forest Bioeconomy and Climate Change*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 197–209.
- Hetemäki, L., Verkerk, H., 2022. Climate-smart forestry approach. In: *Forest Bioeconomy and Climate Change*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 165–172.
- Huttunen, S., Ojanen, M., Ott, A., Saarikoski, H., 2022. What about citizens? A literature review of citizen engagement in sustainability transitions research. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 91, 102714.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2014. *Climate change 2014: Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability*. Cambridge University Press.
- Jandl, R., Ledermann, T., Kindermann, G., Freudenschuss, A., Gschwantner, T., Weiss, P., 2018. Strategies for climate-smart forest management in Austria. *Forests* 9 (10), 592.
- Karlsson, L., Nightingale, A., Naess, L.O., Thompson, J., 2017. ‘Triple wins’ or ‘triple faults’? Analysing policy discourses on climate-smart agriculture (CSA). *CCAFS Working Paper*, (197).
- Kauppi, P., Hanewinkel, M., Lundmark, T., Nabuurs, G.J., Peltola, H., Trasobares, A., Hetemäki, L., 2018. *Climate Smart Forestry in Europe*. European Forest Institute.
- Keeling, C.D., 1960. The concentration and isotopic abundances of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. *Tellus* 12 (2), 200–203. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2153-3490.1960.tb01300.x>.
- Kerr, J., Cheers, J., Gallegos, D., Blackler, A., Kelly, N., 2023. *The Art of co-Design: A Guide to Creative Collaboration*, 1. BIS Publishers.
- Kleinschmit, D., Böcher, M., Giessen, L., 2009. Discourse and expertise in forest and environmental governance—an overview. *Forest Policy Econ.* 11 (5–6), 309–312.
- Kleinschmit, D., Lindstad, B.H., Thorsen, B.J., Toppinen, A., Roos, A., Baardsen, S., 2014. Shades of green: a social scientific view on bioeconomy in the forest sector. *Scand. J. For. Res.* 29 (4), 402–410.
- Laakkonen, A., Zimmerer, R., Kähkönen, T., Hujala, T., Takala, T., Tikkanen, J., 2018. Forest owners’ attitudes toward pro-climate and climate-responsive forest management. *Forest Policy Econ.* 87, 1–10.
- Leipold, S., Petit-Boix, A., Luo, A., Helander, H., Simoens, M., Ashton, W.S., Xue, B., 2023. Lessons, narratives, and research directions for a sustainable circular economy. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 27 (1), 6–18.
- Leipold, S., Luo, A., Simoens, M., Helander, H., Petit-Boix, A., 2024. Can we talk? Disrupting science circles with narrative-led dialogs. *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 153, 103683.
- Lindner, M., Maroschek, M., Netherer, S., et al., 2010. Climate change impacts, adaptive capacity, and vulnerability of European forest ecosystems. *For. Ecol. Manag.* 259 (4), 698–709. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2009.09.023>.
- Lipper, L., Thornton, P., Campbell, B.M., Baedeker, T., Braimoh, A., Bwalya, M., Caron, P., Cattaneo, A., Garrity, D., Henry, K., Hottle, R., Jackson, L., Jarvis, A., Kossam, J., Mann, W., McCarthy, N., Meybeck, A., Neufeldt, H., Remington, T., Torquebiau, E.F., 2014. Climate-smart agriculture for food security. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 4 (12), 1068–1072. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2437>.
- Martin, A., McGuire, S., Sullivan, S., 2013. Global environmental justice and biodiversity conservation. *Geogr. J.* 179 (2), 122–131.
- Masood, E., 2018. The battle for the soul of biodiversity. *Nature* 560 (7719), 423–426.
- Mathys, A.S., Bottero, A., Stadelmann, G., Thürig, E., Ferretti, M., Temperli, C., 2021. Presenting a climate-smart forestry evaluation framework based on national forest inventories. *Ecol. Indic.* 133, 108459.
- McDermott, C.L., 2014. REDDuced: from sustainability to legality to units of carbon—the search for common interests in international forest governance. *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 35, 12–19.
- MEA, 2005. *Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. Ecosystems and Human well-being: Synthesis*. Island Press, Washington, DC.
- Miller, C.A., Wyborn, C., 2020. Co-production in global sustainability: histories and theories. *Environ. Sci. Pol.* 113, 88–95.
- Muhr, M.M., 2020. Beyond words—the potential of arts-based research on human-nature connectedness. *Ecosystems and People* 16 (1), 249–257.
- Muhr, M., Gartner, F., Scherhauser, P., 2024. Walking interviews. *Interdisziplinäre Stadtforschung* II, 53.
- Nabuurs, G.-J., Delacote, P., Ellison, D., Hanewinkel, M., Lindner, M., Nesbit, M., Ollikainen, M., Savaresi, A., 2015. A New Role for Forests and the Forest Sector in the EU Post-2020 Climate Targets. European Forest Institute.
- Nabuurs, G.-J., Delacote, P., Ellison, D., Hanewinkel, M., Hetemäki, L., Lindner, M., 2017. By 2050 the mitigation effects of EU forests could nearly double through climate smart forestry. *Forests* 8 (12), 484.
- Nabuurs, G.J., Verkerk, P.J., Schelhaas, M.J., González Olabarria, J.R., Trasobares, A., Cienciala, E., 2018. Climate-Smart Forestry: Mitigation Impacts in Three European Regions, 6. EFI, Helsinki, Finland, p. 31.
- Newell, P., Srivastava, S., Naess, L.O., Torres Contreras, G.A., Price, R., 2021. Toward transformative climate justice: an emerging research agenda. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Clim. Chang.* 12 (6), e733.
- Nijnik, M., 2010. Carbon capture and storage in forests. In: Hester, R.E., Harrison, R.M. (Eds.), *Carbon Capture: Sequestration and Storage*, the Royal Society, Cambridge, Issues in Environmental Science and Technology, 29. Royal Society of Chemistry, pp. 203–238.
- Norström, A.V., Cvitanovic, C., Lóf, M.F., West, S., Wyborn, C., Balvanera, P., Österblom, H., 2020. Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research. *Nat. Sustainability* 3 (3), 182–190.
- Page, M.J., McKenzie, J.E., Bossuyt, P.M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T.C., Mulrow, C.D., Moher, D., 2021. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 372.
- Papa, C.C., DeLysér, K., Clay, K., Gadoth-Goodman, D., Cooper, L., Kurz, W.A., Ontl, T., 2023. Modeling climate-smart forest management and wood use for climate mitigation potential in Maryland and Pennsylvania. *Front. For. Global Change* 6, 1259010.
- Peltola, H., Heinonen, T., Kangas, J., Venäläinen, A., Seppälä, J., Hetemäki, L., 2022. Climate-smart forestry case study: Finland. In: *Forest Bioeconomy and Climate Change*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 183–195.
- Piazza, N., Malanchini, L., Nevola, E., Vacciano, G., 2024. Where to start with climate-smart forest management? Climatic risk for forest-based mitigation. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 24 (10), 3579–3595.
- Pülzl, H., Wydra, D., Obeng-Odoom, F., Arts, B., Edwards, P., Kleinschmit, D., Giurca, A., Burns, S.L., Mijailoff, J.D., Nurrochmat, D., Park, M.S., 2024. Current forest-related discourses. In: Kleinschmit, D., Wildburger, C., Grima, N., Fisher, B. (Eds.), *International Forest Governance: A Critical Review of Trends, Drawbacks, and New Approaches*, IUFRO World Series, 43. IUFRO, pp. 83–118.
- Ramcilovic-Suominen, S., Pülzl, H., 2018. Sustainable development—a ‘selling point’ of the emerging EU bioeconomy policy framework? *J. Clean. Prod.* 172, 4170–4180.
- Reid, R., 2017. Developing farmer and community capacity in agroforestry: is the Australian master TreeGrower program transferable to other countries? *Agrofor. Syst.* 91 (5), 847–865.
- Rockström, J., Gaffney, O., Rogelj, J., Meinshausen, M., Nakicenovic, N., Schellnhuber, H.J., 2017. A roadmap for rapid decarbonization. *Science* 355 (6331), 1269–1271. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aah3443>.
- Roe, E., 1994. *Narrative Policy Analysis: Theory and Practice*. Duke University Press.
- Santopuoli, G., Temperli, C., Alberdi, I., Barbeito, I., Bosela, M., Bottero, A., Tognetti, R., 2021. Pan-European sustainable forest management indicators for assessing climate-smart forestry in Europe. *Can. J. For. Res.* 51 (12), 1741–1750.
- Scheffers, B.R., De Meester, L., Bridge, T.C., Hoffmann, A.A., Pandolfi, J.M., Corlett, R.T., Watson, J.E., 2016. The broad footprint of climate change from genes to biomes to people. *Science* 354 (6313), aaf7671.
- Seidl, R., Schelhaas, M.-J., Rammer, W., Verkerk, P.J., 2014. Increasing forest disturbances in Europe and their impact on carbon storage. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 4 (9), 806–810. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2318>.

- Seidl, R., Thom, D., Kautz, M., et al., 2017. Forest disturbances under climate change. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 7 (6), 395–402. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3303>.
- Senf, C., Seidl, R., 2021. Mapping the forest disturbance regimes of Europe. *Nat. Sustainability* 4 (1), 63–70. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00609-y>.
- Shephard, N.T., Narine, L., Peng, Y., Maggard, A., 2022. Climate smart forestry in the southern United States. *Forests* 13 (9), 1460.
- Sikkema, R., Wilhelmsson, E., Ellison, D., Petersson, H., 2024. Forest owner attitudes toward climate-proof Forest Management in Sweden and the Netherlands—between Forest strategies and practical measures. *Small-scale Forestry* 23 (4), 693–720.
- Singer, B., Giessen, L., 2017. Towards a donut regime? Domestic actors, climatization, and the hollowing-out of the international forests regime in the Anthropocene. *Forest Policy Econ.* 79, 69–79.
- Stavi, I., Xu, C., Argaman, E., 2024. Climate-smart forestry in the world's drylands: A review of challenges and opportunities. *The Anthropocene Review* 11 (1), 67–90.
- Stone, D.A., 1989. Causal stories and the formation of policy agendas. *Polit. Sc. Quarterly* 104 (2), 281–300.
- Torresan, C., Benito Garzón, M., O'grady, M., Robson, T.M., Picchi, G., Panzacchi, P., Kneeshaw, D., 2021. A new generation of sensors and monitoring tools to support climate-smart forestry practices. *Can. J. For. Res.* 51 (12), 1751–1765.
- United Nations, 2015a. Paris Agreement. . United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/the-paris-agreement>.
- United Nations, 2015b. Transforming our world: the 2030 agenda for sustainable development.. United Nations. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>.
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), 2021. Glasgow leaders' declaration on forests and land use.
- Van Noorden, R., Maher, B., Nuzzo, R., 2014. The top 100 papers. *Nature News* 514 (7524), 550.
- Verkerk, P.J., Costanza, R., Hetemäki, L., Kubiszewski, I., Leskinen, P., Nabuurs, G.J., Potočník, J., 2020. Climate-smart forestry: the missing link. *Forest Policy Econ.* 115, 102164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2020.102164>.
- Wang, G.G., Lu, D., Gao, T., Zhang, J., Sun, Y., Teng, D., Zhu, J., 2024. Climate-smart forestry: an AI-enabled sustainable forest management solution for climate change adaptation and mitigation. *J. For. Res.* 36 (1), 7.
- Weatherall, A., Nabuurs, G., Velikova, V., Santopuoli, G., Neroj, B., Bowditch, E., Tognetti, R., 2022. Defining climate-smart forestry. In: *Climate-Smart Forestry in Mountain Regions*, 40. Springer, pp. 35–58.
- Winkel, G., 2012. Foucault in the forests: A review of the use of Foucauldian concepts in forest policy analysis. *Forest Policy Econ.* 16, 81–92.
- Wittmayer, J.M., Backhaus, J., Avelino, F., Pel, B., Strasser, T., Kunze, I., Zuijderwijk, L., 2019. Narratives of change: how social innovation initiatives construct societal transformation. *Futures* 112, 102433.
- Yousefpour, R., Augustynczyk, A.L.D., Reyner, C.P., Lasch-Born, P., Suckow, F., Hanewinkel, M., 2018. Realizing mitigation efficiency of European commercial forests by climate smart forestry. *Sci. Rep.* 8 (1), 345.